

Additional File 5. Placement of a region of interest (ROI) for the calculation of relaxation time in the kidney's cortex. (a) *In vivo* T_2^* -weighted image of a single kidney post administration of SPION-labelled mMSCs, (b) placement of an ROI (yellow line) covering the cortex of the kidney where cell/SPION contrast is observed and (c) the changes in signal intensity as a function of echo time, with the solid line displaying the exponential fit of the data, from where the relaxation time is derived. Relaxation times were calculated with Paravision 6.0.1.